

**THE LABORATORY IN INTERGRATED SCIENCE TEACHING: A
REVIEW**

By

ADEBIMPE, B., AFOLABI, B. A.

and

AYILARA, T. T.

*School of Sciences
College of Education, Ilorin*

Abstract

Science has become a school subject before the invention of Instruments designed specifically for scientific purposes. Students and teacher of science finds the laboratory a unique place to do all the things i.e. hypothesis through experimentation. Different skills are developed in science laboratories such as identification of problems, asking of questions, observing, measuring, and classify various skills could be achieved in laboratories such as proper organization of Information acquired, thorough, and careful observations of objects within the immediate environment. Many objectives of using science laboratories are stated, so also rules guide the uses of laboratories are itemized.

Keywords: *Laboratory, Integrated, Teaching and Review.*

INTRODUCTION

The Laboratory is a design place where science teachers and other carry out practicals and where interactions between science teacher and students take place. And since science is concerned with finding answers to problems in a bid to understand and interpret natural phenomena, it is often necessary to try out our wise guesses or hypotheses through experimentation. The student or teacher of science finds the laboratory a unique place to do all these things. According Ihde (1964), laboratories were

not usually associated with science teaching before the eighteenth century. Science had become a school subject before the invention of instruments designed specifically for scientific purposes. Most of the scientific equipment in the laboratory before 1600 were borrowed from practical crafts and craftsmen whose tools were much better than those that the scientists used during that period.

Eminent Pioneer scientists of the caliber of Lavoisier (1743 - 1794) Priestly (1776 - 1804) Cavendish (1731 -1810), Dalton (1766 - 1844) converted their homes into laboratories where regular demonstration lectures were held.

As we are already aware, most modern science curricular emphasize students involvement in science teaching through practical work in the laboratories. These include Nigerian integrated science project (NISP) which was developed by the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and the Nigerian Secondary School Science Project (NSSSP) developed by comparative Education Study and Adaptation Centre (CESAC). All of these place much emphasis on laboratory work.

Such emphasis is in keeping with the demand of science which requests certain skills to be developed in the learners. such skills include:-

1. Ability to plan an experiment and analyze the practical problem into its components parts;
2. Ability to perform experiment;
3. Ability to interpret results and draw conclusions;

The following skills are also developed in science Laboratories:-

- (a) Identifying problems
- (b) asking questions
- (c) Formulating hypothesis
- (d) observing
- (e) measuring
- (f) classifying
- (g) communicating
- (h) analyzing data
- (i) Inferring.

Laboratory work and experiment in integrated science classes

Are often discussed as if they synonymous. Take for example, some experiments are performed outside the laboratory just as some laboratory activities cannot be called experiments. While most laboratory activities are conceived in order to provide practice in designing operating and interpreting data, however, experiments are operations or procedures designed for the purpose of testing a supposition, confirming what is already known and discovering the unknown.

Laboratory exercise is an integral part of science teaching, which should be used when

1. laboratory practicals are really needed as a means to verify a scientific principle, a law or a theory already known to the students.
2. it is needed as a means of obtaining and learning scientific information.
3. laboratory practicals can be mashed with text books and other learning activities.

As Bajah (1983), puts it the value of the laboratory work will depend upon the position assumed by the integrated science teacher during integrated science lessons. If he assumes a position of a dispenser of knowledge, he uses laboratory only to drill or verify. While at the opposite extreme, if the teacher assumes the position of a guide to learning and laboratory is used as a place where students discover knowledge from the later role of the teacher in the laboratory instruction is more useful to the pupils going by the way children learn.

Research has shown that children learn effectively only when they are giving the opportunity to learn through doing than when they are simply allowed to observe. They enjoy measuring, manipulating apparatus, making inferences. These processes can only be developed and acquired if learners are allowed to participate in science instruction through laboratory experience.

The concept of Integrated Science Laboratory

The world is a laboratory endowed with the materials phenomena that integrated is interested in and does investigate. The child, in learning Integrated Science, should observe and study the environment first. That is his foremost laboratory. The world is the next natural environment a child comes in contact with after his experiences in the home. Making the child take another look at the environment and investigating the thing in it at school, becomes a lot easier and simpler observations of the known world of the child.

Integrated science however implies more than mere observations of phenomena. Explanations, testing, verification and critical analysis of events, ideas and events are also crucial since the environment does not offer a child. An integrated science corner can be created at one end of the one word to provide additional experiences that the environment is unable to offer the child. A controlled environment in form of a laboratory is necessary for the development of scientific skills, processes and attitudes.

The laboratory and its facilities such as apparatus and chemicals can be used to give the child an opportunity to experience integrated science test phenomena, verify ideas and develop skills and altitudes not possible through nature experiences and exploration only (Bajah, 1978).

The desired outcomes of laboratory programme should be that which make learners to gain insight and experience in designing, manipulating, interpreting and evaluating their own experiments. It sounds reasonable to adopt a unified approach to studying the three basic sciences. In simple terms, when scientific concepts are taught as integrated principles, the following objectives are inten:-

- i. Providing scientific concepts which will be relevant to the child's need and experiences.

- ii. Stressing the fundamental unity of science.
 - iii. Preparing the children adequately for future study in science related areas.
 - iv. Relating science education to cultural values of contemporary society.
- In practical situations of the school system, the objectives of teaching integrated science using laboratory will include training the children in acquiring the following skills:-
- a. Thorough and careful observations of objects within their immediate environment.
 - b. Accurate and complete reports of what have been observed.
 - c. Proper organization of information acquired.
 - d. Using information acquired as basic for generalization.
 - e. Ability to continue with the process of inquiry when new data are different from those predicted.

Improvising Suitable Materials for Integrated Teaching and Learning Concept of Improvisation

Improvisation has become imperative for the teaching and learning of integrated science. More so that the economic situation makes the cost of materials and apparatus very high.

The usual reason for the poor equipping of integrated science laboratory seems to be a challenge to teachers today. Even if material and equipment are available, the increasing enrolment of students into school still pose the problem of insufficiency of these materials for integrated science teaching to be effective every students should be given the opportunity to handle materials of science and experience science personally.

The teacher is confronted with the challenge of being creative in ensuring good use of whatever types and numbers of science materials and

apparatus that may be available, the teacher is also challenged to be innovative in his teaching. His creativities will enhance a lot his efforts in trying to use alternative methods and resources in teaching the course. The teacher can mobilize his learners and work together in trying to imbibe the idea of improvisation to solve the problem of lack of and inadequate facilities for integrated science teaching and learning. Improvisation means a lot of things. According to Ango (1990), improvisation rightly conceived means.

- a. substituting something (a tool) in a place of another to serve a unique function.
- b. Converting a tool material or equipment into another form.
- c. Altering a device or idea to serve a different function.

Basic Tools for Improvisation

1. Basic articles from the home such as bottles of various shapes.

- Empty tins
- Used razor blades
- Used soup plates
- Old news papers.

2. Materials from hardware shops

- Plastic
- Glue
- Nails

3. From Goods Market

- Ammonia
- Bleaching power
- Starch
- Seeds.

4. **From Medicine (drugs) Stores**

Medicine dropper

Boric acid

Iodine

Dyes

Thermometer

5. **From Optical Shop**

Old eyes glasses lenses

Lenses

Reading glass lenses.

The Need for Laboratory in the Teaching of Integrated Science

It is a fact that integrated science laboratory is a neglected, aspect of science education. Not enough has been done to ensure the right integrated science is taught and handled by the right person. It is of paramount importance that integrated science is taught properly at our schools to give children a sound foundation in this vital aspects of their education.

Laboratories should be erected as separate buildings for experiencing integrated science in schools. Any piece of knowledge can be taught meaningfully to any child at any level provided the knowledge is brought to his level.

The aim emphasized in advocating for laboratories at school is a vital role for suitable learning environment. Science taught through laboratory approach, however, stimulates the natural way children acquire understanding, (Aderson and Voelker 1990), children need to be made aware of their environment and what is happening there. Awareness comes through sharing and not through showing.

To every willing person is the joy of discovery and with feeling comes understanding. It is hereby advocated for a re-examination of science

foundation, especially a consideration of mandating all levels of schools to build separate rooms called laboratories for any successful implementation of science curriculum, appropriate facilities are necessary. These facilities must be used appropriately in order for the aim of integrated science to be achieved. There is a big need therefore to design, organize and manage a science room in every level.

Locating and Designing the Laboratory

Working in the laboratory demands a high degree of concentration, as well as freedom from disturbance and distraction. Poisonous and dangerous materials may be released while work is going on. It is therefore advisable to locate laboratory away from the busy roads, games field, hostels.

In designing a laboratory, provision should be made for the following;

- (a) The main laboratory - for discussion lectures and practical
- (b) Ancillary rooms – such as the preparation room and stores.

Storage and Management

For ease of retrieval, apparatuses should be stored in an orderly manner according to the topics for which they will be required. It is important that the locations of apparatuses be indicated by means of big, bold labels on the shelves or drawers containing them.

Frequently used articles like metre rules, thermometers and glass wares, should be located in the most readily accessible places. All apparatus allocated to students should be numbered for easy identification.

Safety Equipments

Every laboratory should have the following safety equipment and materials:-

- a. At least one fire extinguisher

- b. Buckets of sand
- c. Fire blankets.
- d. Fire alarm.
- e. Respirators
- f. Gloves.
- g. Accident book
- h. Safety poster.

General Precaution

1. On their first day in the laboratory, students be given a safety talk by the teacher who should emphasized the need for caution in using the laboratory and discuss the safety rules with them.
2. They should not be allowed to enter into the laboratory unless the teacher is around.
3. Students should not be allowed to crowd the demonstration bench.
4. The doors leading out of the laboratory should be opened outwards and should never be locked when laboratory is occupied.
5. All reagents bottles should be labeled.

Safety Rules

1. Avoid eating or smoking in the laboratory
2. All cuts and scratches be covered with water proof plaster before working in the laboratory.
3. Always wash hands, using soap before leaving the laboratory.
4. Chemicals must not be tasted and should be smelled with care.
5. Gas leakages should not be tested with naked flames but with soap solution (Greedy, 1972).

Conclusion

Integrated Science laboratory is not confined to a room with sinks and other fittings for experiencing of it. It is a place in the fields and streams near the school or a room specially equipped and set aside for the purpose it is intended.

A laboratory should be a place where children learn the process of skills of science and generate knowledge about their surrounding. The teacher of integrated science should help children to make adequate use of laboratory, employing their knowledge and to enable them to stand on what they know and deep into the unknown. Improvisation should as well be encouraged to help the laboratory look like one, furthermore the rules guiding the management of laboratory should be adhered to by all the children. Laboratory should not be erected where there is a lot of distraction.

Keywords: Effects, Guided-discovery, Expository method, Performance, Biology

REFERENCES

- Anderson, D et. al (1990) Developing children's thinking through science
Prentice Hall Inc Englewood Cliffs New Jersey (1990).
- Ango, M. L. (1990) Basic Science Laboratory Ehindero (Nigeria)
Limited.
- Bajah, S. T. (1978). Meaning and Philosophy of Integrated Science. JSTN, 16, 2
pp 3 -15
- Bajah, S. T. (1983). Teaching integrated science creatively. Ibadan University
press(c).
- Greedy, J. A. (1972). Laboratory manual for schools and Colleges.
Heineman Educational Books Limited, London.
- Ihde, A.J. (1964). The development of modern chemistry. New York: Harper and
Row.
1. Avoid eating or smoking in the laboratory
 2. All cuts and scratches be covered with water proof plaster before
working in the laboratory.
 3. Always wash hands, using soap before leaving the laboratory.
 4. Chemicals must not be tasted and should be smelled with care.
 5. Gas leakages should not be tested with naked flames but with soap
solution (Greedy, 1972).